

Developing a mutualized R&D for network organizations based on Living Lab methods: the transformation of Sion military airport into a commercial airport

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Abstract

When faced with a radical disruption, a firm must be innovative regarding its new services in order to survive. In the particular case of industrial firms, this goes traditionally through R&D departments. In the field of services, it is more complicated because the production and the consumption happens simultaneously and always involves the consumer as a co-creator of value (Vargo & Lusch, 2004). In the context of this research project, we aim to develop a newly conceptualized framework for adapting the R&D function to the service sector based on Living Lab methods. The R&D function could be externalized since usually the customer journey is based on an unordered series of touchpoints involving different service providers with the active participation of customers. A living lab is often presented as being at the junction of open and user innovation. We thus propose a new model where the living lab is integrated into the formal framework of the “à la Frascatti” R&D process in order to break the linearity of the latter by including co-creation. This model allows the living lab to be better accepted in typical “industrial mentalities” and, due to the formalism of the R&D process, to rely rather on systematic and rigorous academic disciplines (for exploration, experimentation and evaluation) than on less formal practitioner approaches. The case study of the renewal of Sion Airport will be presented in this paper to test its feasibility. There is a major disruption in its service offer, transforming it from a military to a touristic airport. So, all kinds of services have to be developed from scratch. For instance, the Lab organized last year the mandatory crash plane simulation on the tarmac, required by the Federal Office of Civil Aviation (FOCA). In this paper, we present an applied research project, which is about the creation of a reception area more accessible, welcoming and functional for crews and their passengers of business jets.

Keywords: *Living Labs, Service Design, Airport Services, Tacit Knowledge*

1 Context

"Aviation - Sion airport shattered the statistics on Saturday. 647 passengers transited by the capital. Sion airport feels like it's growing wings. On Saturday, the infrastructure beat his record with 263 plane movements. Last year's record was 185 movements. Of this total, 63 movements are business jets. If we add the test link with London, the Sion airport saw 647 passengers transiting during the day of Saturday." (www.lenouvelliste.ch, February 12, 2017).

Inaugurated in 1935, Sion airport is ideally located in the heart of the Swiss Alps and close by the largest tourist resorts in Valais such as Crans-Montana, Verbier, Zermatt and Saas Fee. Until 2017, Sion airport was essentially a military airport. Since the army decided to leave Sion airport and to concentrate the aviation sector in another region, the airport will transform radically its offer toward the tourism sector. It will propose more scheduled air services, business and commercial flights. Today, Sion airport faces thus a major touristic challenge. Indeed, tourism in Wallis needs its infrastructure in order to evolve and meet growing demand of travelers. The current infrastructure does not respond to this evolution. The number of passengers and flight frequencies are also no longer the same as when it was first operated nearly a hundred years ago. The airport needs R&D activities in order to provide innovation in its services and adapt to this disruption in its business model.

This case study research is particular in the sense that the aim of the living lab here is to "revive" an airport originally intended for military purposes, which must be transformed as quickly as possible into a profitable commercial airport. The living lab by its logic of co-creation and co-production constitutes a process of innovation, which is completely adapted to this type of challenge. The living lab is here directly embedded in the transforming ecosystem (from a military to a commercial airport). Usually living labs are designed as a catalyst for a region (i.e. macro level). In this case the living lab (meso level) is integrated in a formal R&D framework to gain immediate acceptance from all the stakeholders. The purpose of the living lab in this particular context is to create the types of services needed at a commercial airport. All these services already exist at other airports. Consequently, the objective is therefore through co-creation to adopt a rapid transformation of the airport. We generally tend to apply field studies as well as quasi-experiments to enhance the design of "tacit knowledge" of airport operations in the context of digitalization. To do so we rely on approaches coming from social sciences such as survey research, conjoint analysis, ethnomethodology, human ethology, experimental phenomenology, visualization techniques, social experiments ... We describe in this paper one of the activities (micro level) undertaken by the living lab and which concerns the design of the passenger reception area.

The well-known Frascati Manual was the first attempt (its first edition was published in 1920) by OCDE to formalize the research and development function in manufacturing. R&D is not fundamental research, nor even applied research. It is defined as "experimental development". It is a formal process, which accumulates specific knowledge that can be transformed into commercial applications. R&D "à la Frascati" has been adopted by every

industry in the world. At the time of its origin, it was essentially a matter of sovereign economic power. Over the years, the R&D process has become standardized, based on a linear sequence (exploration, design, development, testing and scaling-up). It is typically conceived for make-to-stock logistics. From Chesbrough and the open innovation paradigm, the barriers of the firms have opened to integrate external knowledge and ideas (2004). Today, most of the innovative initiatives are intended for the service sector. A service represents an intangible production and is typically not adapted to the strict linear R&D process. Vargo & Lusch go one step further with its service dominant logic paradigm and affirm that every industry is a service industry. The product is only a vehicle to transfer the value to the customer. The customer is always a co-creator of value as no value is created if the product is not consumed (2004). There is thus an urgent need to revisit the Frascati Manual to devise an effective R&D function along with relevant performance metrics specific to the service sector to facilitate the dissemination of innovations. In this paper, we develop a new kind of R&D for Sion airport based on Living Lab methods. Indeed, Sion airport represents a reunion of multiples SMEs and public entities in one location. It has thus to work in a collaborative manner, integrating all co-design the stakeholders in the of new innovative services.

The main applied research question addressed in this paper is "Sion Airport: How to make the reception area for crews and their families more accessible, welcoming and functional?" The reception hall of Sion airport is no longer up to date. Since its creation, no renovation work has been carried out.

The methodology explains somehow the common thread. The pilot project has been preceded by qualitative interviews with all the stakeholders who frequent the premises of the airport, including employees of the companies. An immersion program took also place to observe the actual services. Then, different Service Design tools were applied in order to co-develop the service: writing a screenplay, creating blueprints and sharing a theatrical experience. This pilot project is finally presented in 3D, with the Kozikaza program. This project corresponds to the discovery of the necessities indispensable to the development of the commercial infrastructure at Sion airport. It focuses on the travel experience and therefore, only on the airport lobby, including the information desk.

This paper is organized as follows. In Section 2, we present a literature review related to the notion of R&D for services. In Section 3, we describe the concept of the R&D for services based on Living Lab methods that has been implemented. In Section 4, we focus on one of the pilot projects that we realized and that is related to the new airport lobby. In Section 5, we conclude and provide directions for further research.

2 Literature review

The Taylor model, first instituted in industry, calls for standardizing and simplifying tasks as well as emphasizes repetition. Service enterprises have tended to base their organizational

models on models from the manufacturing and industrial sectors that incorporate hierarchy, task repetition, and the standardization of procedures. By extension, service companies have relied on traditional service design models that consist of sequential multiphase approaches, beginning with idea generation and proceeding stepwise to concept development, business analysis, prototype testing, market testing, and commercialization (Stuart and Tax, 2004). In turn, organizations have sought to simplify work-related issues in order to maintain continuity and solve problems by training employees to rehearse and practice routines (March, 1991). Those routines constitute a source of not only efficiency, but also stability and predictability within organizations, since employees can cope with new situations by applying routines with which they are already familiar (Starbuck, 1993).

Today, however, such models present clear limitations. Above all, the Taylor organizational model, which originated in the industrial world, is no longer relevant in today's service and knowledge-based economy. In its volatile environments that seek increased heterogeneity, it becomes increasingly difficult to develop, disseminate, and apply routines. Standardization that once achieved success might be inappropriate at another time and therefore cause inefficiency.

We have long known that a firm has to be innovative in order to survive in such volatile environments (Drucker, 1954), in which innovation a new product development are critical for any firm's survival and growth (Penrose, 2009). According to Teece et al. (1997), it is not only a unique set of resources that matters but an organization's ability to constantly adapt, reshape, reconfigure, and innovate. To obtain unique resources (i.e., dynamic capabilities), organizations should be based upon highly firm-specific processes and shaped by specific asset positions (Gawer and Cusumano, 2002). To put a name to such resources, Den Hertog et al. (2010) have defined service innovation capabilities as dynamic capabilities of transferring and imitating.

Knowledge is a dynamic capability since "learning allows tasks to be performed more effectively and efficiently, often as an outcome of experimentation, and permits reflections on failure and success" (Ambrosini et al., 2009). According to Drucker (2009), knowledge has become both the key economic resource and the dominant source of competitive advantage. Considered an important firm resource that is unique, inimitable, and valuable (Grant, 1997; Wernerfelt, 1984), knowledge exerts a positive influence on the probability of innovating (Gopalakrishnan et al., 1999). A knowledge-based service refers to a service delivered by highly trained providers that offer high-quality services designed to meet customers' needs (Debély et al., 2006). In knowledge-based services, intellectual capital embedded in people and systems is critical (Oliveira et al., 2003). That evolution implies a different organizational model that relies more on creativity and implicit knowledge, which is the essence of expertise.

In our project, we seek to demonstrate how expertise and creativity have become essential to today's value-added services. Service offerings need to encompass the following elements by relying on the provider's knowledge, not a Taylor model-inspired process:

- A clear, thorough understanding of the needs and expectations of clients;
- The ability to elaborate a diagnosis of clients' needs from limited information;
- The outline of a specific service proposal, co-created with the stakeholders;
- The efficient use of delivery processes and existing products or product modules;
- A custom-made solution that incorporates perceived benefits, often referred to as problem resolutions; and trust among the stakeholders, including the customers.

In each step of implementing that process, expertise should be transparent. Evidently, however, the functional flow chart of the Taylor model was not created around such reasoning.

The underlying principle of the knowledge-based view is that the foundation of an organization's performance is its ability to generate, combine, recombine, and exploit knowledge (Kogut and Zander, 1996). Knowledge, especially tacit knowledge, is scarce and difficult to transfer and imitate (Winter, 1987). Because tacit knowledge is embedded partly in the psyche and intuition of individuals (Brown and Duguid, 1998; Grant, 1996), it is not readily articulated and resists codification (Baumard, 1999). Although tacit knowledge is also difficult to identify, interpret, formalize, and transfer, all of which processes can be expensive, the high value of tacit knowledge motivates organizations to attempt to capture it (Spiegler, 2000). After all, the challenge of readily codifying tacit knowledge affords it the potential to create a sustainable advantage for individuals and organizations that possess superior knowledge bundles (Lubit, 2001). At the same time, in a problem-solving context, applying explicit knowledge without also applying tacit knowledge can result in suboptimal solutions. Since tacit knowledge is a latent asset unless constantly and systematically enacted, organizations have to invest continually in updating their skills and experiences (Daft and Weick, 1984; Orlikowski, 2002).

Bartol and Srivastava (2002) have defined knowledge sharing as an action in which members of an organization disseminate relevant information to other people in the organization. Tacit knowledge, held by individuals or the group, is learned by observation, imitative application, participation in routines, and personal experience (McIver et al., 2012). If tacit knowledge is subconsciously understood and applied, then it is usually shared via highly interactive activities (Zack, 1999) and created during collaboration (Hardy et al., 2003; Lee and Choi, 2003). Generally, the transmission of knowledge occurs implicitly, in formal meetings and on-the-job training, meaning that social factors, particularly trust, are crucial in the transfer of tacit knowledge (Collins and Hitt, 2006). As a first step, direct interaction facilitates the identification of people with the appropriate knowledge (Lee and Cole, 2003).

The continuous sharing of knowledge contributes to innovations in teams, units, and entire organizations. To better execute innovative tasks, members of organizations always have to search for explicit knowledge already existing in the organization or borrow from the tacit knowledge of colleagues. That latter process is crucial to developing a network of face-to-face interactions. Indeed, agents of R&D in the service sector are often responsible for that function and perhaps even part of that function in different organizations (Holste and Fields,

2010; Lin, 2007). Accordingly, it is necessary to foster a willingness to share knowledge, especially tacit knowledge, that can be acquired only via training and rehearsal. In that sense, a knowledge-sharing approach has to be implemented throughout the organization; it needs to be part of the organization's culture. Only then are members of organizations encouraged to learn and share ways of executing tasks, to be committed to problem solving, and to take initiative (Hu et al., 2009). The pivotal role of direct interaction among the actors toward value co-creation is described in details by Grönroos & Voima (2012).

3 A model for mutualized R&D for services

The classic process of manufacturing innovation follows three steps in a linear manner: research, R&D and finally manufacturing. In the field of Service Science the raw material of service production is considered to be knowledge (explicit and implicit) and the customer is also a co-producer. These two special features of service production make it impossible for the innovation process to be strictly linear, as in manufacturing. Typically, a service is performed in any order. As such, the logic of service innovation must consider that the associated process cannot be linear, as it must include reciprocating patterns of interaction among the participating stakeholders. R&D for production is based on the "make-to-stock" principle. The goods are produced in batches, then stored and finally sold on the markets. On the other hand, in a service environment, for instance university students will develop specific skills by following a pedagogical script that includes regular interactions with professors, assistants and researchers.

If we consider now the iterative "Living Lab" process with its four components: 1. co-creation, 2. exploration, 3. experimentation and 4. evaluation. This process differs from the R&D process only in the co-creation component, which breaks the linearity of the process and involves every stakeholder taking part in the innovation. Indeed, the living lab is often presented as an innovation process at the junction of open innovation and user innovation. The Living Lab represents then a "co-creation enabler" between user and open innovation. By analogy, we could say that exploration, experimentation and evaluation, even if they are tools that are service-oriented, have the same similar roles and purposes as the identification of needs, prototyping and testing in the classical R&D manufacturing process. We propose a model that combines the Living Lab process with the classical R&D process (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. Integrating living lab methods in the more formal R&D process

Both processes (i.e. R&D and LL) contribute to the overall innovation framework. The living laboratory process integrates the necessary co-innovation components within service operations. R&D enjoys very high acceptance among the stakeholders in the airport ecosystem since its tools are grounded on engineering and scientific methods. Exploration, experiment and evaluation could also be based on scientific methods, typically field studies and laboratory testing in the context of services such as cultural anthropology, ethnography, quasi-experiment ... The living lab would then be more accepted by all stakeholders, especially in an ecosystem like an airport where innovation is driven by security, safety and compliance. In this context, a rigorous and systematic (i.e. scientific) process is of great importance (e.g. mandatory crash test of an airplane that is required, monitored and evaluated by the aviation authorities in order for the airport to obtain an operating license).

To understand how the R&D process is synonym to innovation in industry, we propose a detailed account of the Frascati Manual. In the Frascati Manual (2015, p. 28), R&D is defined as “creative and systematic work undertaken in order to increase the stock of knowledge – including knowledge of humankind, culture and society – and to devise new applications of available knowledge.” A R&D activity is characterized by five criteria: novel, creative, uncertain, systematic, transferable and/or reproducible. The goal of R&D is to create new knowledge. R&D is performed systematically, in “a planned way, with records kept of both the process followed and the outcome”. (Frascati Manual, p. 46, 47). According to SNA (System of National Accounts), in the Frascati Manual (2015, p. 28), “product refers to a good or a service and process refers to the transformation of inputs to outputs and to their delivery or to organizational structures or practices.” In the new edition of the Frascati Manual, a greater emphasis is given to the R&D in the social sciences, humanities and the arts (2015, p. 44). R&D in service is difficult to define. R&D project are rarely “specific to a service” and there is

no clear distinction “between R&D and other innovation activities”. Furthermore, in service companies, R&D is not formally organized as in other industries (Miles 2007, Sundbo 1997). Some indicators like collaboration with public research laboratories, staff with doctoral degrees or doctoral students and the publication of research findings in scientific journals help to identify R&D in service. (2015, p. 68, 69).

For Sawatani and Fujigaki (2015, p. 166-168), these characteristics are not enough to describe R&D in service. They propose a Service R&D Model based on the S-D logic and extended the Moeller’s model where “service processes are divided into facilities, transformation and usage”. The new model has “three spheres, such as R&D, value co-creation and site”. In this model, researchers benefit of ideas generated through the co-creation interaction. The Living Lab approach, “an Open Innovation ecosystem”, have also the goal to involve user in the R&D process as a co-creation value (Pallot, et al. 2011). However, as Ballon et al. (2005) show in their framework, Living Labs are little concerned with in-house R&D.

R&D for service needs a clearer definition and more formalized process to be identified easily. In this context, design could play an interesting role. However, “design and R&D activities are difficult to separate” (Frascati, p. 63, 64). Sanders and Stappers (2008) proposed a design research landscape with two dimensions: the design research approach and the mindset. Based on this work, Pallot et al. (2008) propose a landscape of Living Lab research with two dimensions, the interaction mode and research type, to show “a progress form functional tests and usability analysis toward user-co-creation” and proposed two complementary dimensions to “better characterize the current R&D and innovation trends and evolution”. Another dimension could show the shift from technological to sociological innovation (Pallot, 2010). However, these landscapes do not fully define R&D for service.

Because Design Thinking process is not performed systematically, it means “in a planned way, with records kept of both the process followed and the outcome” (Frascati Manual, p. 46, 47), it cannot be considered as R&D. The proposed methodology for service design in four steps as the advantage to be more systematic and, so, can increase the knowledge and be transferable and/or reproducible.

After the explanation of the overall concept of R&D for services based on living lab methods (see Figure 1), we show practically how we implement the R&D part (exploration, experimentation and evaluation).

The exploration phase, based on proven qualitative research methodologies, allows the descriptive and analytical study of the field, the service and the problem (Crewsell, 2013). Approaches such as ethnomethodology, ethology or phenomenology are carried out through semi-directive interviews, focus group interviews, immersions, social experiments, benchmarks and actor maps. Innovation is the capacity to generate novel and useful ideas, and to transfer it to market. It is a critical component of successful design in today’s business economy. Chan et al. (2011) argued that innovation can be best achieved in the ideation

phase, where concepts and ideas are generated either intuitively or through systematic processes. Based on collected data, this analysis and design phase is based on tools from service marketing, such as Customer Journeys, Service Blueprints, scriptwriting, user stories. It allows the best representation of the utility of the service and its functionalities to generate the tangibilisation of the service experience. Once the service has been designed and scripted, it can be prototyped and staged using tools such as theatre or mock-ups. A prototype is a visualization of the service containing an understanding of what the solution should be and what it should do for users (Blomkvist, 2014). Initial user feedback can be collected to improve the service prototype and to make the invisible visible). The employed methodology at this level is based on quasi-experiment, where participants are not randomly assigned to a case (Shadish et al., 2002), after which the results of the two groups are compared (Campbell & Stanley, 2015). Knemeyer and Naylor (2011) have identified the necessary conditions for quasi-experiments to establish the causality of two tested variables; first, with all else equal, only the independent variable should be changed, and second, the independent variable has to affect the participants, and the dependent variable has to intervene. The quasi-experiment phase is also staged such as in a theater re-enactment in order to facilitate the scaling up of the tested service (Fragnière et al., 2012). To allow clients to judge the quality of the service and decide to market it, a 1:1 scale test is organized. This phase measures its quality through feedback from users and potential auditors, evaluates its price and the willingness to pay (Homburg, 2005). This is a scientific, evidence-based, approach (Carr et al. 2011). This evaluation process is similar to a patient visit to a doctor in 3 steps (Simon, 1990): Examination, including anamnesis (analysis of the initial situation and stipulation of functions) consists in gathering and understanding information in order to identify the problem (internal data as well as tacit knowledge). Each element is measured so that the main problem can then be calculated and defined in the problem statement. Diagnosis (inventory and mapping, problem modelling) is the problem-solving phase. The problem is structured by performing a contradiction and error source analysis using the most effective problem-solving techniques. The prescription corresponds to the solution evaluation phase. The ideas generated are evaluated based on the evaluation of the solution. By giving priority to ideas and formulating local constraints, the ideal solution will then be formulated. This final result consists of a list of possible innovative conceptual solutions. If solutions are still not found after the elimination of contradictions, or another new problem occurs after the evaluation of the solution, the problem-solving process is reinstated in the first step to redefine the original situation.

After this phase services can be implemented for real and this corresponds to the service production (see Figure 1).

4 An example of service innovation based on LL integrated in the more formal R&D process

This case study is focused on the meso level proposed by Schuurman: “Living Lab Innovation

project” as it is intended to generate a managerial impact for the airport. The novelty is also to integrate service design tools at the micro level, these tools have been tested in another LL research (Papilloud & al., 2017) but are not often mobilized in Living Lab environments.

We have worked on a dozen of service design projects to enable the transformation of Sion airport. In this paper, we concentrate on how to make the reception area more accessible, welcoming and functional for crews and their passengers of business jets.

To illustrate that process, the case of regular Swiss flights that will land and depart from Sion Airport offers a fitting example. Since the infrastructure currently in place cannot accommodate such a large number of passengers, new operating modes offering a series of services (e.g. security checks and dining facilities) that can accommodate more passengers need to be designed, tested, and implemented. All these new operating modes must also be orchestrated into a consistent experience.

The R&D for Sion airport is first a physical location. The lab is a large renovated theatre fully IT equipped used to simulate services experiences for design and innovation. In our R&D activities, we are especially interested in the way service companies are able to scale up their new services once created. In the classical setting of a manufacturing company, we all know that the innovation process is realized through the R&D function. In the case of services, however, the approach is very different since a service is an intangible production, does not follow a strict linear process, and usually involves different providers. As ultimately the service will be experienced by customers, the innovation process resembles more closely practicing music scales, training to play a sport, rehearsing a scene, or working out a dance routine. In a service experience like going to the airport to take a plane, the routines are called “operating modes” and are orchestrated in such a way that the passenger undergoes without any difficulties a very complex process (baggage handling, security check, duty free shopping, boarding). In these ways, the R&D function in the service sector certainly corresponds more to a kind of general staging of both providers and clients. Consequently, in order to provide services of good quality, the rehearsal of new services is critical to being able to innovate.

We have thus developed a conceptual framework grounded on theory building to enable the acquisition and coordination of the necessary know-how (i.e., tacit knowledge) to foster service innovation. Thanks to a Memorandum of Understanding with Sion airport, we are able to conduct the conclusive experiments in real-life conditions. Thus, this research in general typically corresponds to in-use research. Its originality lies in the fact that to our knowledge no such conceptual framework for R&D exists today that has been tested in real conditions.

A Living Lab can be seen as a “living laboratory”, at the level of a region, in which users participate in the development of innovative products and services (co-creation). Its main goal is to explore the “insight,” that is, the salient features valued by a specific population, so that new services emerge. It is also a test environment, open and benefiting from technological and methodological tools. It is, therefore, an ecosystem allowing a participatory process, using appropriate tools and methodologies (Liedtke et al., 2012). Service Design was not

integrated in the living lab research landscape (Pallot & al, 2011), it could play an important role for innovation in the traditional service industry.

The methodology followed for the realizing this pilot project was to conduct, in a first stage, a qualitative survey among passengers at Sion airport. To this end, 15 passengers were interviewed on 18 February 2017 during their flights between the cities of Sion, London and Zurich. Then a second qualitative study was carried out among Sion airport employees. In March, 5 employees as well as the airport manager, were interviewed. A complementary methodology used was immersion (participative and non- participative observation). Indeed, the passenger experience from the entrance hall to boarding could be lived, in February, during the actual flights. A transcript of these interviews was made in order to imagine a scenario and to create an initial blueprint as well as an improved blueprint considering the remarks and details received during the qualitative interviews and the immersion. Then based on a "LivingLab" (co-creation) approach, we developed together an experiment design that ultimately took place in our labs. Finally, in order to test the improved blueprint proposal, a theatrical experiment was set up as well as a final 3D pilot project.

The objective of this work was to submit a pilot project for the implementation of new 3D infrastructures for the passenger waiting area, in order to respond to this constant evolution described above. The implementation recommendations are illustrated by a 3D pilot project divided into several presentation themes (see Figure 2): the opening of a souvenir and coffee shop, the creation of different spaces, the improvement of the partners' visibility, the improvement of the information office - the C office and the addition of an interactive terminal.

Figure 2. Some photos illustrating the pilot project

5 Conclusion

In the knowledge economy, the experience becomes the central part of value co-creation and “the market is becoming a forum for conversation and interactions between consumers, consumer communities, and firms. It is this dialogue, access, transparency, and understanding of risk benefits that is central to the next practice in value creation.” (Prahalad & Ramaswamy, 2004). Thanks to our partnership with Sion Airport, we have the opportunity

to test Service Design tools such as the blueprints in real Living Lab conditions, thereby making the smooth transfer of findings into practice possible via practical operating modes. Consequently, the results would be tangible and able to be disseminated in other contexts. As mentioned, the business model for the tourism sector especially needs complete revision. The conclusions we can draw from this living experience were not at all anticipated. The direct integration of a living lab into the airport's R&D function implies that R&D is based on a formally coherent scientific process (i.e. a systematic and rigorous approach) and accepted in industry. As we have already mentioned in this article, the living lab is an interface between open innovation and user innovation. What we have seen in this case study is that a living lab, formally integrated into the R&D function, immediately gains credibility and legitimacy and adds the missing component of traditional R&D, namely co-creation between the user and a collective of service providers. Indeed, managing an airport requires the coordination of various activities such as a tight schedule integrated into a very formal logistics driven by goals of safety, security and compliance. User experience is certainly crucial, as for example any response to an airport accident that involves the airport, the police, firefighters, passengers, airlines and even the state, the municipality, journalists, social networks... to achieve a complex problem solving to save people's lives.

We thus propose a mixed innovation process where the living lab is integrated into the formal framework of the R&D function. This mix of the two innovation processes offers the advantage for R&D to integrate co-creation and the advantage for the living lab to be embedded in a formalized process based on evidence-based approaches and which enjoys great credibility and legitimacy in the industrial world.

In all, the project could represent an original, concrete initiative toward applying the logic of R&D to services based on Living Lab method. Thanks to our partnership agreement with Sion Airport, we have been able to develop expertise in service innovation dedicated to small airports for tourism. In that sense, Sion Airport, previously a military airport that will essentially become a commercial one, presents an interesting case for several reasons. Since all services have to be created, tested, put into production, and priced, the airport will serve as a to-scale laboratory that can enable us to develop and test a comprehensive method for service innovation.

What is missing from that cooperative symphony, however, even if the musical partition is beautiful and the musicians talented, is a conductor who can make everyone—providers, locals and tourists—play in unison. An airport is indeed a combination of multiples actors (SMEs, public entities, passengers ...). This is where Living Lab methods can play an important role as a facilitator in the future of service innovation of typical network organizations such as an airport. By applying the Living Lab precepts (co-creation approach), we develop on a regular basis, involving all the stakeholders, experiments. A Living Lab can be seen as a "living laboratory", at the level of a region, in which users participate in the development of innovative products and services (co-creation). Its main goal is to understand the "insight," that is, the specific needs of the customers, so that new services emerge. It is also a test

environment, open and benefiting from technological and methodological tools. It is, therefore, an ecosystem allowing a participatory process using appropriate tools and methodologies.

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